

Designing a Roadmap for Effective and Sustainable Strategies for Assessing and Addressing the Challenges of EU Agriculture to Navigate within a Safe and Just Operating Space

Potential savings from NTM harmonisation

Discussion paper

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ACRONYMS

INT: International

NTM: Non-tariff measures

REG: Regional

RO: Regulatory Overlap

SPS: Sanitary and Phytosanitary measures

1. INTRODUCTION

The adoption of Sanitary and Phytosanitary (SPS) measures acts as a double-edged sword for developing countries, creating high compliance costs (Disdier et al., 2008; Essaji, 2008) while simultaneously driving investment and quality upgrades (Maertens & Swinnen, 2009; Olper et al., 2014). While preferential trade agreements can foster regulatory convergence, the available evidence suggests that aligning with international standards provides greater economic benefits compared to regional standards (Disdier et al., 2015; OECD, 2016). This is because conformance with stringent international standards grants access to multiple markets thereby avoiding redundant trade costs (Cadot & Gourdon, 2016; Barrett, Reardon, Swinnen & Zilberman, 2020) and fostering scale economies. Adopting regional standards, however, requires specific adaptation measures and associated compliance costs, while they reduce market diversification (Czubala *et al.*, 2009).

This paper provides empirical support for the heterogeneous trade impact of SPS measures as a function of the countries' stage of economic development. A key novelty is that it quantifies the potential trade cost savings attained by closer regulatory frameworks, distinguishing between SPS measures that are more generally adopted (i.e., international) and those that are less prevalent across trading partners and products (i.e., regional). For this purpose, this research is aided using the UNCTAD TRAINS non-tariff measures (NTM) inventory, where a regulatory overlap index (UNCTAD, 2017) is constructed that identifies, for each of regional and international SPS regulations, a measure of similarity between trading partners. Given the qualitative nature of data, the split between international and regional SPS measures is done on the basis of their spread across countries and sectors.

A structural gravity equation that includes both international and domestic trade is specified, improving not only theoretical consistency but also allowing for the identification of the trade effect of non-discriminatory SPS measures (Heid, Larch and Yotov, 2021). The specification is flexible enough to allow for country-specific trade effects (i.e. interacting variables of interest with exporter and importer trade shares) (Kee and Nicita, 2022). To gain further insights, the sample is segmented into three groups according to the stage of economic development of the exporter. Furthermore, a panel dataset is used which allows the inclusion of country-pair fixed effects (FE), as a way to minimize endogeneity concerns. Analysis is based on a panel dataset that covers bilateral agrifood trade (disaggregated in 24 HS2 chapters) between 102 exporters and 87 importers, in three-year intervals between 2011 and 2017.

2. EMPIRICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1. Data

NTM

The Global UNCTAD NTMs database (UNCTAD, 2018)¹ is used as a source for the SPS and Regulatory Overlap (RO) variables (RO is explained in Section 2.2.). This database registers 41 4-digit categories² of SPS measures in agrifood sectors (HS 2-digit between 01 and 24), from which 18 can be defined as 'behind the border' measures. Behind the border measures are also applied domestically, could be subject to harmonisation and include those measures classified as 'process' and 'product' by

¹ This version of data was downloaded from the UNCTAD webpage in November 2021.

² We use the terms '4-digit SPS categories' and 'measures' interchangeably. Furthermore, in the empirical application, the term SPS measures restricts itself strictly to behind the border regulations defined in section 2.1.

Ederington and Ruta (2016). More specifically, these measures are maximum residue limits (NTM code A2); packaging and labelling (A3); hygiene (A4); production and post-production (A6); and conformity assessment (A820) (see Table 3 in the Appendix).

Studies on international harmonisation are very specific (e.g., pesticide residues), which enables a comparison of the country-specific regulation with internationally accepted standards (e.g., Codex Alimentarius). Given the qualitative nature of our SPS data, this type of ‘metric’ comparison is infeasible. Nonetheless, an inspection of the data reveals that of the 18 categories, seven SPS categories exhibit considerably higher global recognition (across countries and sectors) and are considered as a proxy for an internationally recognised standard. In particular, we classify as ‘international’ those categories that fulfil *at least two of* the following conditions: being adopted by more than 70% of the countries, affecting at least 98% of the HS6 product lines, and covering at least 40% of the observations. Upon these criteria, we therefore refer to the set of seven SPS measures as ‘international’ (INT), and the remaining eleven as ‘regional’ (REG). (see Table A1 in the Appendix).

SPS data is provided at HS 6-digit sectoral disaggregation and are mainly recorded as non-discriminatory (i.e. applied by each importer j to all trade partners), showing the stock of measures in place in the year of data collection. Nonetheless, following Sanjuán et al. (2023) there is still some bilateral and temporal information that is exploited to build up a panel for the period 2010-2020. The initial built-in SPS database includes 720 HS6 product lines, that are further aggregated into HS2 chapters 01 to 24 by averaging across HS6, per importer, exporter and year.

Trade

The main importers and exporters in each HS2 chapter are identified originally in a complete trade dataset, sourced from UN ComTrade, and those traders that jointly account for 99% of each HS2 chapter are selected. Countries in the sample are presented in Table 4 in the Appendix.

Domestic trade

The application of a structural gravity approach requires domestic trade (Yotov et al., 2016), which is usually proxied by the difference between production and exports. This paper follows Sanjuán et al., (2023) by employing the ‘domestic sales’ and ‘exports’ flows in the Global Trade Analysis Project (GTAP) database. The GTAP dataset provides observations for 21 agrifood sectors, corresponding to HS2 chapters 01 to 24, for years 2004, 2007, 2011, 2014 and 2017 (version 11). To split the ‘domestic sales’ into each HS6 product line, one calculates the ratio of ‘domestic sales’ to ‘exports’ per product, exporter and year. In a subsequent step, this ratio is applied to each of the HS6 product lines within the GTAP commodity definition (according to the GTAP-HS6 mapping, using the H3 nomenclature, provided by WITS). Due to computational expense, the final estimation is conducted at HS 2-digits, such that both international and domestic trade are aggregated up to HS2, per exporter, importer and year.

Other data

In addition to the SPS explanatory variable, two additional policy variables are considered: bilateral tariffs and membership of a Regional Trade Agreement (RTA). Bilateral tariff data is taken from UNCTAD TRAINS and the RTA data is from CEPII (Conte et al., 2022).³

The final panel dataset includes 102 exporters, 87 importers, 720 HS6 sectors aggregated into 24 HS2 chapters, for the years 2011, 2014 and 2017. Intra-EU trade is excluded from the analysis, because of its large trade weight, accounting for more than 40% in some specific sectors (chapters 01, 04, 06 and 19), and approximately 30% of global agrifood trade in the sample. Furthermore, in the EU either

³ Both trade and tariffs are accessed through WITS (World Integrated Trade Solutions) is a World Bank databases platform <https://wits.worldbank.org/>

perfect harmonisation or mutual recognition of SPS regulations are in place, which together with the large trade weight, might bias the results.

2.2. Model specification

The analysis is based on the gravity equation, consistent with several trade theories (Bergstrand et al., 2015) and estimated with the Poisson pseudo-maximum likelihood (PPML) estimator, which not only allows one to preserve zero-trade values, but also avoids inconsistent coefficient estimates in the presence of heteroscedasticity (Santos Silva and Tenreyro, 2006).

The empirical model is specified as:

$$m_{ijst} = \exp[\alpha_0 + \beta_{TAR}TAR_{ijst} + \beta_{RTA}RTA_{ijt} + \beta_{SPS} \cdot SPS_{ijst}^c + \sum_{k=i,j} (\beta_{SPS,k} \cdot SPS_{ijst}^c \cdot SHR_{kst}) + \sum_{k=i,j} (\beta_{RO,k} \cdot SPS_{ijst}^c \cdot RO_{ijst} \cdot SHR_{kst}) + \sum_t \beta_{BORDER,t}BORDER_t + \gamma_{ij} + \gamma_{it} + \gamma_{jt} + \gamma_{st} + \varepsilon_{ijst}] \quad (1)$$

where the subscripts i, j, s and t refer to the exporter, importer, sector (at HS 2-digit level), and year, respectively; the superscript c refers to the category of SPS measure, with $c =$ ALL, INT (international) or REG (regional), as defined in Table A1 in the Appendix; m is bilateral trade; TAR is the power of the bilateral tariff expressed as a percentage (AdV) such as: $TAR = \ln(1+AdV/100)$; RTA is a dummy that captures the presence of regional trade agreements; $BORDER_t$ is a dummy to signal international trade flows in years $t=2014$ and 2017 (for $t=2011$, the $BORDER_t$ variable is dropped to avoid multicollinearity). Domestic trade flows are included (i.e. observations with $i=j$), for which TAR and RTA value 0.

The variable SPS indicates the number of Sanitary and Phytosanitary measures (i.e. 4-digit categories). The impact of SPS measures on trade is modulated by the interaction with the regional overlap variable, RO (UNCTAD, 2017). RO is measured as the proportion of SPS measures applied by the importer that are also applied by the exporter on its imports (i.e., equivalent to those applied domestically (UNCTAD, 2017)). RO is bounded between 0 (absence of similarity or overlap) and 1 (perfect overlap) and is asymmetric (i.e., for a pair of countries, RO differs depending on which country is the importer and the exporter). In the absence of the application of SPS measures, the exporter does not need to incur additional costs to meet the importer's regulations, and consequently, RO is assigned a value of 1. RO varies by country-pair, sector and year. Compared with symmetric regulatory distance indicators (e.g., Cadot et al., 2018) the RO variable is better suited to address the asymmetry in market access conditions or regulatory convergence. Moreover, RO allows one to calculate the cost savings due to regulatory similarity as both SPS and RO are measured on a common scale. The number of SPS measures, RO and tariffs are first obtained at HS-6 digit disaggregation and then averaged per HS2 chapter. For domestic routes, SPS takes a value of 0 and RO assumes a value of 1.

The variable SHR_k is the world market share of the exporter ($k=i$) and importer ($k=j$) of product s in year t , which allows for heterogeneous impacts of SPS and RO across bilateral routes (Kee and Nicita, 2022; Cadot et al., 2018), by replacing specific average values of the respective shares in the chosen route. Furthermore, the country-sector-year specific market shares nests in one single variable the multiple country-sector-year FE that some authors recommend when using sectoral disaggregated data (Yotov et al., 2016) to account for sectoral specific 'multilateral resistance terms' (Anderson and van Wincoop, 2003). Instead, we complement the country-sector-year specific market shares with exporter-year (γ_{it}), importer-year (γ_{jt}) and sector-year (γ_{st}) FE. Only international trade flows are used in the calculation of these trade shares.

A panel structure alleviates some of the identification problems faced by cross-section estimations. In particular, the panel setting allows for the inclusion of exporter-importer (γ_{ij}) FE to control for the potential endogeneity of the SPS policy (Anderson and Yotov, 2016; Baier and Bergstrand, 2007). Additionally, sector-year FE (γ_{st}) control for any sector-year unobserved effects (i.e. global price spikes or shortages), while the time-varying country FE control for country-time specific variables (i.e. GDP,

inflation). Potential endogeneity due to omitted variables is therefore highly alleviated by the inclusion of the rich array of FE together with the market share interactions.

The coefficients on the continuous SPS variable and its interactions with RO are semi-elasticities (Cameron and Trivedi, 2010). To calculate average semi-elasticities for a specific route, the interacted variables are replaced by the mean values for each specific route. The elasticity is calculated by multiplying the semi-elasticities by average values of the respective variables (SPS, RO). Finally, the AVE for a 1% change in the number of SPS measures and RO, is calculated as the ratio of the trade elasticity to the tariff elasticity (Kee and Nicita, 2022), where the latter is borrowed from Fontagné et al., (2022).

3. RESULTS

3.1. Data description

Figure 1 shows the evolution of key variables using the longer time series from 2010 to 2020, with the sample selected set of countries. In panel a, global exports (blue line) and low and lower-income country exports of agrifood commodities have increased over the period at an interannual rate of 4% and 5%, respectively. Notwithstanding, the trade share of lower income countries has remained stable at approximately 10%. Confirming previous literature (e.g. Hummels and Klenow, 2005), exports from low and lower-middle income countries are considerably less diversified (panel b) both in terms of products exported (i.e. HS6 lines) as well as destinations targeted, although following the general trend observed in the period, the number of destinations has increased, on average, from 27 to 31 per HS2 chapter.

In the same period, the number of SPS measures applied have consistently increased (on average across sectors and country pairs) from 2.3 to 3.5, with the number of SPS faced by lower income countries approximately 0.10-0.20 points above the global average (panel c). This upward trend is explained by increases in the number of both international and regional measures (panel d and e). The Regulatory Overlap has fluctuated around 57% for all countries, whilst from the maximum of 54% for lower-income countries in 2011, it has drifted downwards toward 51% in more recent years (panel c). The same trends are observed for 'international' SPS measures, while the downward trend in 'regional' RO is more evident (panel d and e).

Figure 1. Evolution of trade, trade diversification, Prevalence of SPS measures and Regulatory Overlap.

Source: Own elaboration based on UNCTAD (2018) and UN ComTrade. SPS: sanitary and phytosanitary measures; RO: Regulatory Overlap; ALL: refers to all SPS measures; INT: internationally applied SPS measures; REG: regionally applied SPS measures (see definition in main text).

3.2. Estimation Results

The results of equation (1) for SPS and RO for all 18 categories (ALL), and the subsets ‘international’ (INT) and ‘regional’ (REG) (defined in Table A1), are presented in Table 1. Estimation is conducted separately for international- and regional measures due to substantial correlation between both. To detect the presence of heterogeneous trade effects of SPS measures and RO by development stage beyond the nuances implied by the trade shares, the estimation for the full sample is complemented with estimations for three subsamples, each of them restricted by group of exporters according to their economic development classification (see Table 4 in the appendix for countries classification).

With the exception of the higher-income subsample, all models show a negative and significant effect of tariffs on bilateral trade, which is of largest magnitude in the sample of low-income exporters. Thus, a 1% increase in the power of the tariff does not affect exports from high-income exporters, reduces bilateral trade from upper-middle income exporters by 0.36%, while low-income exporters witness a

trade reduction of 0.61% (see Table 1, columns ALL in (4), (3) and (2), respectively)⁴. The coefficient on RTA is mainly positive but non-significant. The country-pair FE are probably capturing most of the RTA effect given the short time span of data. Neither border variable is statistically significant in the subsample of low-income exporters, indicating that international/domestic trade has remained stable with respect to the base year 2011. In contrast, border variables for 2014 and 2017 are statistically significant in the upper-middle group, whilst only significant in 2017 for the high-income group. The observed negative sign implies that on average, in comparison with the base year 2011, international trade has declined relative to domestic trade, which suggests a reversed globalisation trend (Yotov et al., 2016).

The coefficient of SPS is negative and significant in all models and samples, meaning that in the absence of regulatory overlap with the importer's regulations and when trade shares are null, SPS measures reduce bilateral trade. Looking at the coefficients on the SPS interactions, one observes that the final trade impact of SPS measures depend significantly on the relative trade shares of the exporter and the importer. More precisely, the larger the exporter and the importer, the smaller the trade impact of SPS measures *ceteris paribus*⁵, and this result applies irrespectively of the income level of the exporter. Thus, on the one hand, the larger the trade share of the exporter in the global trade of a given commodity, the easier it is to comply with the importer's regulations and consequently, the smaller is the trade loss due to SPS measures (Kee and Nicita, 2022). Indeed, larger exporting countries also have larger exporting firms which suffer less from restrictive SPS measures (Curzi et al., 2020). On the other hand, the regulatory burden imposed by SPS measures can be more intensely alleviated by access to larger importers as there are reduced possibilities for exporters to divert trade (Kee and Nicita, 2022).

The size of the importer positively affects the final trade impact of RO (i.e. significant coefficient on the SPS-RO interaction with the importer trade share) in the full sample, while across subsamples mixed effects are observed: a non-significant coefficient in the low-income group, positive and significant in the high-income group and both negative and significant (INT) and non-significant (REG) in the upper-middle group. Consequently, setting domestic rules in high-income exporters closer to those imposed by larger importing countries (versus smaller importing countries) can boost bilateral trade more intensely. The interactions of SPS-RO with the exporter trade shares are only significant in a few cases and can be both positive (in the upper-middle group of exporters) and negative (in the low-income group). Thus, larger upper-middle-income exporters seem to benefit more than small upper-middle income exporters from converging to international regulations (model (3), second column). In contrast, the size of the exporter is statistically found to negatively affect the final trade impact of RO in the group of lower-income exporters, for both international and regional SPS measures. Thus, the larger the trade share of the low-income exporter the greater is the detriment to trade from regulatory converge with the importer. This result suggests that regulatory harmonisation can damage lower-income exporters, which may be due to substantial fixed and compliance costs implied in the short term, particularly in those sectors more dependent upon export markets.

To simplify the interpretation of results in the presence of several interactions, the SPS and RO trade effects can be better judged by calculating the coefficients (i.e. semi-elasticities) at average values of the trade shares and RO/SPS variables and then computing trade elasticities by multiplying the semi-elasticities by average values of SPS and RO, respectively.⁶

⁴ Note that this tariff elasticity is exploiting mainly the time variation, while internationally accepted tariff elasticities for modelling purposes like the ones by Fontagné et al., (2022) or GTAP (based on Hertel et al., 2007) exploit the cross-country variability, leading to much larger values (in absolute terms).

⁵ This interpretation draws from positive and highly significant coefficients on the SPS-SHR interactions in all specifications while the coefficients on SPS are negative (see Table 1).

⁶ As the RO variable varies between 0 and 1, the elasticity is more meaningful than the semi-elasticity.

On average, the trade elasticity of all SPS measures is -0.264, being of larger magnitude for international than regional measures (model (1) in Table 1). Thus, a 1% increase in the number of international and regional measures reduces bilateral trade by 0.238% and 0.199%, respectively. This pattern is driven by the influence of high-income exporters, as the elasticities in the high-income subsample are very similar to those in the full sample (-0.266, -0.236 and -0.180, for all, international and regional SPS measures, respectively). It should be noted, however, that when considering semi-elasticities, a one-unit increase in the number of regional SPS measures reduces trade relatively more compared with a one unit increase in international SPS measures (in all income groups).

In terms of regulatory overlap, the trade elasticities are not of a large magnitude neither in the full sample nor the high-income exporters subsample but still suggest certain trade gains amongst those countries with closer regulatory frameworks. Thus, in the whole sample, the trade elasticity is on average 0.018, with a range between 0.013 and 0.022 for 'international' and 'regional' measures, respectively. This apparent larger benefit of converging to regional rather than international measures disappear when focusing on segmented subsamples. Thus, the RO elasticities for international and regional measures are close to each other in the subsample restricted to high-income exporters (0.031 and 0.033, respectively), while in the subsample restricted to upper-middle income exporters the RO elasticities are 0.056 and 0 for international and regional measures, respectively. Interestingly, upper-middle-income exporters are those that suffer less from SPS measures and benefit more from convergence to the importer's regulations, particularly when the importer applies international rules.

In the subsample of low-income exporters, two main issues are observed that contrast with exporters in other income groups. First, the negative trade impact of regional SPS measures is more intense, with a trade elasticity of -0.405 versus -0.173 for upper-middle income and -0.180 for high-income exporters. Furthermore, regional SPS measures are also more trade-restrictive than international ones (elasticity of -0.178) amongst lower-income exporters, while the opposite effect is observed amongst higher-income exporters. Secondly, regulatory overlap with trade partners does not benefit low-income exporters, although convergence to 'international' rules do not damage trade as much as convergence to 'regional' rules. Thus, a 1% increase in regulatory overlap with the importer's rules decreases bilateral exports from lower-income countries by 0.11%. When these rules are international, the reduction in trade is 0.09%, while when they are regional, trade falls by 0.14% (model (2) in Table 1).

The empirical literature contains several papers that find either limited or even negative trade impacts of harmonisation, although this is usually found in the case of higher income exporters (Moenius, 2006; Shepherd, 2015). Interestingly, our results agree partially with those of Disdier et al. (2015) who report a negative impact of harmonisation clauses in RTAs for exports from lower- to higher income countries when convergence is promoted toward the regional measures applied by the richer importers. Similarly, Santeramo & Lamonaca (2022) observes a negative effect of harmonization provisions on bilateral trade between RTA signatories.

Table 1. Estimation results of the Structural Gravity equation.

	(1) Full sample			(2) Low & Lower-middle income exporters			(3) Upper-middle income exporters			(4) High-income exporters		
	ALL	INT	REG	ALL	INT	REG	ALL	INT	REG	ALL	INT	REG
TAR	-0.192***	-0.191***	-0.199***	-0.612***	-0.617***	-0.623***	-0.356***	-0.353***	-0.345***	-0.009	-0.008	-0.018
	(0.041)	(0.039)	(0.045)	(0.062)	(0.063)	(0.066)	(0.054)	(0.053)	(0.057)	(0.046)	(0.045)	(0.049)
RTA	0.094	0.102	0.087	-0.009	-0.028	0.031	0.050	0.067	0.103	0.130	0.119	0.149
	(0.066)	(0.063)	(0.072)	(0.124)	(0.127)	(0.112)	(0.080)	(0.078)	(0.093)	(0.099)	(0.094)	(0.107)
SPS	-0.141***	-0.183***	-0.429***	-0.157***	-0.189***	-0.632***	-0.137***	-0.193***	-0.388***	-0.142***	-0.185***	-0.418***
	(0.018)	(0.026)	(0.041)	(0.033)	(0.045)	(0.093)	(0.025)	(0.034)	(0.062)	(0.022)	(0.030)	(0.054)
SPS x SHR_i	1.630***	2.563***	3.684***	1.188***	1.582***	3.173***	0.579***	0.941***	1.894***	0.573***	1.080***	1.285***
	(0.150)	(0.187)	(0.414)	(0.112)	(0.155)	(0.302)	(0.111)	(0.148)	(0.277)	(0.156)	(0.214)	(0.323)
SPS x SHR_j	1.165***	1.645***	4.020***	0.693***	1.287***	2.114***	1.132***	1.599***	2.835***	1.014***	1.552***	3.801***
	(0.144)	(0.198)	(0.422)	(0.205)	(0.299)	(0.533)	(0.133)	(0.179)	(0.367)	(0.234)	(0.313)	(0.657)
SPS x RO x SHR_i	-0.019	-0.408	1.403	-0.730***	-0.763***	-3.267***	0.972***	0.941***	1.311	0.115	-0.228	0.794
	(0.257)	(0.322)	(0.975)	(0.157)	(0.182)	(0.611)	(0.228)	(0.244)	(0.862)	(0.200)	(0.259)	(0.574)
SPS x RO x SHR_j	0.548***	0.494**	2.243***	0.595	0.572	1.939	-0.684**	-0.833**	1.869	1.042***	1.052***	3.105***
	(0.193)	(0.249)	(0.533)	(0.399)	(0.462)	(1.405)	(0.345)	(0.407)	(1.234)	(0.230)	(0.354)	(0.636)
BORDER_2014	0.026	0.026	0.008	-0.003	-0.040	-0.038	-0.210***	-0.189***	-0.214***	-0.010	-0.002	-0.007
	(0.025)	(0.024)	(0.025)	(0.125)	(0.121)	(0.132)	(0.070)	(0.068)	(0.077)	(0.034)	(0.033)	(0.036)
BORDER_2017	-0.087**	-0.091**	-0.055	-0.029	-0.089	0.006	-0.245**	-0.210**	-0.206*	-0.185***	-0.195***	-0.094*
	(0.043)	(0.039)	(0.046)	(0.162)	(0.152)	(0.168)	(0.102)	(0.093)	(0.109)	(0.055)	(0.054)	(0.050)
Semi-elasticity ^a												
SPS	-0.087***	-0.104***	-0.273***	-0.081***	-0.074*	-0.506***	-0.054**	-0.080**	-0.224***	-0.093***	-0.107***	-0.270***
	(0.018)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.029)	(0.040)	(0.082)	(0.023)	(0.032)	(0.059)	(0.022)	(0.030)	(0.049)
RO	0.031***	0.021**	0.033***	-0.203***	-0.159***	-0.226***	0.150***	0.103***	0	0.061***	0.046***	0.046***

	(0.011)	(0.047)	(0.000)	(0.044)	(0.038)	(0.042)	(0.044)	(0.037)	-	(0.014)	(0.016)	(0.009)
Elasticity^b												
SPS	-0.264***	-0.238***	-0.199***	-0.261***	-0.178*	-0.405***	-0.169**	-0.189**	-0.173***	-0.266***	-0.236***	-0.180***
RO	0.018***	0.013**	0.022***	-0.109***	-0.092***	-0.142***	0.077***	0.056***	0	0.039***	0.031***	0.033***
Observations	245,958	245,958	245,958	56,163	56,163	56,163	79397	79397	79397	121,977	121,977	121,977
R²	0.941	0.941	0.940	0.938	0.938	0.938	0.94	0.94	0.93	0.94	0.94	0.94

Notes: Robust standard errors clustered by exporter-importer-HS2 sector in parentheses. *** p < 0.01, ** p < 0.05, * p < 0.1. All models include exporter-importer, exporter-year, importer-year and HS2 sector-year FE. R²: is the McFadden pseudo R². Estimation is conducted in Stata, using the command *ppmlhdfe* by Correia et al., (2020). ^a Semi-elasticity (i.e. coefficients) calculated at mean values of the interacted variables, using the *nlcom* command in Stata, standard errors calculated with the Delta method in parentheses, replacing by 0 non-significant coefficients (at 10%) involved in the calculation. ^b Elasticities obtained by multiplying the semi-elasticity by the average (excluding domestic trade) SPS and RO, respectively.

3.3. Ad-valorem equivalents per income group

Table 2 transforms the SPS/RO elasticities shown in Table 1 into AVEs using a tariff elasticity of -4.865, which is obtained averaging the 709 HS6-specific tariff elasticities within HS2 chapters 01-24 estimated by Fontagné et al. (2022) (excluding non-negative and non-significant at 1% tariff elasticities). More precisely, AVEs are calculated from (i) a 1% increase in the number of SPS measures and (ii) the savings (or extra cost) attained by increasing RO by 1%. The AVEs are shown for the full sample (model (1) in Table 1) and restricted samples by income-group of the exporter (models (2) to (4) in Table 1).

Table 2. Ad-Valorem Equivalents of SPS measures and RO, by income group of the exporter

	(1) Full sample			(2) Low & Lower-middle income			(3) Upper-middle income			(4) High-income		
	ALL	INT	REG	ALL	INT	REG	ALL	INT	REG	ALL	INT	REG
SPS	5.43%	4.89%	4.10%	5.36%	3.67%	8.33%	3.48%	3.89%	3.55%	5.48%	4.86%	3.70%
RO	-0.37%	-0.27%	-0.45%	+2.24%	+1.89%	+2.92%	-1.57%	-1.16%	0%	-0.79%	-0.64%	-0.67%
RO saving	7%	5%	11%	0%	0%	0%	45%	30%	0%	14%	13%	18%

Notes: The tariff elasticity used in the AVE computation is -4.865 (average based on HS6-specific estimations by Fontagné et al. 2022). Results based on SPS and RO elasticities reported in Table 1.

SPS: Sanitary and Phytosanitary measures; RO: Regulatory Overlap; ALL: refers to all SPS measures; INT: internationally applied SPS measures; REG: regionally applied SPS measures (see definition in main text and composition in table A1).

The resulting AVEs in the full sample (columns (1) in Table 2) are 5.4% on average for all SPS measures, being slightly higher for ‘international’ (4.9%) than ‘regional’ measures (4.1%). These figures are relatively small in comparison with estimates found in the literature, which range between 5 and 27% (Kravchenko et al., 2022; Kee and Nicita, 2022; Gourdon et al., 2020; Cadot et al., 2018; Ghodsi et al., 2016; Kee et al., 2009), which is probably due to the inclusion of domestic flows in our estimations. Similarly, the average reduction in the SPS trade cost due to RO is 7%, being larger for regional (11%) than international measures (5%), but with very modest AVEs values (less than 1%).

The AVEs of SPS measures for high-income exporters closely approximate those for the full sample, (5.5, 4.9 and 3.7 for all, international and regional SPS measures, respectively), with the difference that regulatory overlap accounts for greater savings (14, 13 and 18%, respectively). Upper-middle income exporters face slightly lower SPS AVEs (around 4%), with a significant saving (30%) achievable by harmonising to international rules. Low-income exporters, in comparison, face higher SPS AVEs further intensified by additional AVE costs of harmonisation, particularly in relation to regional measures (+2.9%).

Figure 2 presents the AVEs of SPS faced by low-income exporters when exporting to countries of different income level. These calculations are based on the elasticities of model (2) in Table 1. Low-income exporters face the highest trade costs due to SPS measures when accessing high-income countries. On average for all SPS measures, the AVE is 6.4%, with international measures being significantly less costly (4.2%) than regional ones (10.8%), while the respective figures when exporting to either upper-middle or low-income countries are around 4,3 and 4-5%. These results support the idea that the stringency of SPS regulations increases with income level, either de jure or de facto (through stricter enforcement) (e.g. Kee et al., 2009; Disdier et al., 2008; Murina and Nicita, 2017). Kravchenko et al. (2022) find, however, an inverse relationship between income level and the AVEs of technical NTMs, which the authors ascribe to relatively more efficient trade facilitation measures in place, that offset such regulatory costs in lower-income countries.

Figure 2. Ad-valorem equivalents of SPS measures faced by low-income exporters, by income group of the importer.

Notes: AVE calculations for SPS and RO based on the sample restricted to low-income exporters (model (2) in Table 1).

4. CONCLUSIONS

Main conclusions can be summarised as follows:

- (1) the sample segmentation unmasks specific results by development group that would otherwise remain hidden within the pooled sample;
- (2) the inclusion of domestic trade in the gravity specification results in lower trade costs being attached to SPS measures in comparison to a model where only international flows are accounted for. In other words, in the absence of domestic trade, SPS trade costs are upward biased;
- (3) the selected SPS measures impose higher trade restrictions for poorer exporters which only translate into moderately higher ad-valorem equivalents (AVEs) (5.4% and 3.5% on imports from low- and upper-middle-income countries, respectively). The choice of a more recent sample period may explain why some barriers found in earlier works may now be less restrictive, for example, due to the deployment of technical assistance programs, or trade facilitation measures (Kravchenko et al., 2022).
- (4) regional SPS measures restrict trade from lower-income countries more than international SPS measures with respective AVEs of 8.3% and 3.7%, reaching 10.8% and 4.2% when exporting to high-income countries, reflecting the specific adaptation and compliance costs, but also a reduction of market diversification (Czubala et al., 2009).
- (5) gains from harmonisation are not equally distributed, as pointed by Cadot and Gourdeon (2016). Thus, moderate savings are accrued by high- and upper-middle exporters, with SPS trade cost savings of between 0.6 and 1.6 percentage points per each percentage increase in regulatory similarity, while harmonisation damages trade amongst low-income exporters, and with more intensity when harmonising to regional than international SPS measures, in accordance with Disdier et al. (2015) and Santeramo and Lamonaca (2022).

The main policy implication is that, in the absence of other cooperation mechanisms, like technical assistance, poorer trade partners of the EU (or other high-income importers) may not be sufficiently encouraged to adopt the EU's stricter SPS regulations given the lack of trade gains following harmonisation.

As a final cautionary note, the qualitative nature of SPS data and its translation into numeric indicators is challenging. The split between international and regional SPS categories is contingent upon the sample used (sectors and countries). Moreover, although pragmatic considerations have been applied, the international/regional split cannot be as precise as indicators based on quantitative data (i.e. MRLs established by each country in comparison to the Codex Alimentarius).

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APPENDIX

Table 3. Behind the border SPS categories

4-digit SPS category	UNCTAD NTM description	Own Classification	% Countries applying (total = 87 importers)	% HS6 sectors affected (total = 720 HS6 sectors)	% obs. Affected (N = 255,405) ^a
A2: Tolerance limits for residues and restricted use of substances					
A210	Maximum Residue Limits	INT	89%	95%	51%
A220	Restrictions on substances	INT	85%	99%	46%
A3: Labelling, marking and packaging requirements					
A310	Labelling	INT	87%	99%	55%
A320	Marking	REG	56%	92%	16%
A330	Packaging	INT	83%	99%	41%
A4: Hygienic requirements related to SPS conditions					
A410	Microbiological criteria of the final product	INT	80%	95%	40%
A420	Hygienic practices during production	REG	70%	96%	29%
A490	Hygienic requirements n.e.s.	REG	30%	96%	8%
A5: Treatment of elimination of plant and animal pests and disease-causing organisms in the final product or prohibition of treatment					
A510	Cold or heat treatment	REG	31%	46%	4%
A520	Irradiation	REG	6%	75%	1%
A530	Fumigation	REG	22%	22%	2%
A590	Other treatments	REG	33%	86%	5%
A6: Other production and post-production requirements					
A610	Plant-growth processes	REG	16%	85%	2%
A620	Animal-arising or -catching processes	REG	30%	88%	4%
A630	Food and feed processing	REG	66%	94%	30%
A640	Storage and transport conditions	INT	71%	98%	23%

A690	Other requirements	REG	33%	96%	10%
A8: Conformity assessment					
A820	Testing requirements to assess conformity with SPS rules	INT	91%	98%	47%

Source: Own elaboration based on UNCTAD (2018, 2019). SPS categories identified with only 1-digit in the database are excluded. Percentages in the sample (excluding domestic routes). ^a The sample size is larger than the estimation sample as several observations are dropped in the estimation stage.

Table 4. List of exporters and importers and income classification

Income Group	Exporter & importer
High	Austria, Bahrain, Belgium, Canada, Chile, Croatia, Cyprus, Czechia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hong Kong, Hungary, Ireland, Israel, Italy, Latvia, Luxembourg, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland, United Arab Emirates, United Kingdom, Australia, Japan, Korea, Lithuania, Mauritius, Netherlands, New Zealand, Panama, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Saudi Arabia, Singapore, Sweden, Trinidad and Tobago, United States of America, Uruguay
Upper-middle	Belarus, Brazil, Bulgaria, China, Colombia, Costa Rica, Ecuador, Guatemala, Indonesia, Jamaica, Kazakhstan, Argentina, Azerbaijan, Jordan, Lebanon, Malaysia, Mexico, Paraguay, Peru, Russian Federation, Thailand, Turkey
Low & Lower-middle	Bolivia, Burkina Faso, Côte d'Ivoire, Ethiopia, India, Lao, Niger, Togo, Cambodia, El Salvador, Kyrgyzstan, Nepal, Nicaragua, Nigeria, Pakistan, Senegal, Tunisia, Zimbabwe, Viet Nam
Income Group	Only as exporter
High	Kuwait, Malta, Qatar, Oman
Upper-middle	Botswana
Low & Lower-middle	Afghanistan, Algeria, Bangladesh, Benin, Cameroon, Ghana, Guinea, Honduras, Mali, Morocco, Philippines, Sri Lanka
Income Group	Only as importer
High	Brunei Darussalam
Low & Lower-middle	Occupied Palestinian territory

Notes: Income group according to World Bank classification in June 2020.

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